

The Development and Significance of Father–Child Relationships in the family

Dilyayra Nurmurodovna Ro'ziyeva

Independent Researcher at Bukhara State University, Teacher of English at the “Languages Study”, Department of the Bukhara Academic Lyceum of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

Abstract: This article provides: just like being a mother, being a father is no easy task. Based on the number of single dad romance novels published each year, we definitely like seeing our heroes in the role of nurturer and protector, and fall hard for the ones who are overwhelmed but have good intentions. They add depth to the stories and enhance the characterization of the heroes.

Keywords: strength, wisdom, unconditional friend, sources of wisdom, relationships, motivations.

Introduction

Father characters can be some of the most compelling figures in literature, playing pivotal roles as pillars of strength, sources of wisdom, or, in some cases, complex figures with their own sets of flaws and struggles. Writing fathers that are believable and memorable demands a delicate balance of understanding their roles, motivations, and relationships within the story. There is yet another intrusion into the home that needs to be mentioned. It is an unwise father who carries to his family his daily business cares. They disturb the peace existing there. He should leave his worries at the office and enter his home with the spirit of peace in his heart and with the love of God burning within him. If there is friction, his presence should soothe it. If there is turmoil, he should resolve it.

To be a father means to brighten the innocent eyes of a child, to walk alongside them on the path of life, and to be there for them, truly.

I have a friend, a businessman in this city, who does special ordinance work in the temple. One day I passed him on the street and asked where he was going. “I’m going to the temple. Inside those thick walls, in the quiet serenity of that lovely building,” he said, “I find peace.” Then he added, “There is only one other place in the world where I can find peace—in my own home.” What a compliment to his wife! What a compliment to his children! What a credit to him. This should be the ideal for all fathers—to so live that we can find peace in our homes.

Thus, the relationship between father and child develops along with the child’s growth and changes in different stages of life. Each age has its own unique, evolving, and specific characteristics, and father child relationships continually encounter new challenges and opportunities.

Methodology

Fathers, draw close to your children. Learn to communicate. Learn to listen. This means giving a father's most valuable commodity—time! Only good results occur when a father interviews his sons and daughters regularly. He can know their problems and their hopes. He can align himself with them as their unconditional friend. To the extent we become friends with our children in unconditional love, to that extent we become like our Heavenly Father.

A father is a teacher. The Lord has commanded sons and daughters to honor their parents and to give heed to their counsel. The words that open that great volume of scripture, the Book of Mormon, ought to be our guide as fathers: "... having been born of goodly parents, therefore I was taught somewhat in all the learning of my father."

Someone has said: "There is no need of searching out your genealogy if you do not know where your children were last night." Many inspiring suggestions enliven this practical course of study for fathers. I heartily commend this course to strengthen fathers for better spiritual leadership.

Discipline is part of the process of governing children. The Lord has told us how:

"Reproving betimes with sharpness, when moved upon by the Holy Ghost; and then showing forth afterwards an increase of love toward him whom thou hast reproved, lest he esteem thee to be his enemy."

There has been no better statement of a father-child relationship. When a father wisely corrects his son, it proves his love. Only the unwise foolishly indulge their sons and withhold proper discipline.

And finally, the father is to be an example of the highest Christian virtues. To walk uprightly in the admonition of the Lord requires not only patience and forbearance, but an exercise in constant practice of all the Christian virtues by each family member. Perhaps the Lord knew this when he instituted the family. A man needs the responsibility of a wife and family. He needs the responsibility of being an example of righteousness. There is wisdom in this requirement. This kind of gentle persuasion is needed to keep a father "on course" and gently guide him toward perfection.

The father is the symbol of rules and discipline. Only the father can ensure the proper development of both sons as men and daughters as women. When the father's role is reduced to mere provision or punishment, the balance in upbringing is disturbed.

Over the past two decades there has been a shift in the balance between basic and applied research goals in fatherhood studies. Earlier interest in fathers was driven by an overwhelming desire to acquire basic knowledge in a relatively new area of scientific inquiry. Currently, the quest for basic knowledge on the nature, antecedents, and consequences of father-child relationships is paralleled by growing interest in the translation of research findings into effective programs and policies that support and promote positive father-child relationships. The research-to-policy link on fathers is bidirectional: Political emphasis on the importance of fathers fosters the research agenda just as evidence regarding paternal impact influences social policies and program initiatives.

Results and discussion

Fathers' Roles Although descriptive accounts of fathers' relative accessibility to children are informative, they fall short of elucidating what fathers do when they are available and why they do what they do. In this regard, a fuller conceptualization of fathers' roles and the origins of their presumably prescribed responsibilities is warranted. Historical, cultural, and familial ideologies inform the roles fathers play and undoubtedly shape the absolute amounts of time fathers spend with their children, the activities they share with them, and perhaps even the quality of the father-child relationships. In earlier times, fathers were viewed as all-powerful patriarchs who wielded enormous power over their families (Knibiehler, 1995), and vestiges of these notions

continued until quite recently. According to Pleck and Pleck (1997), for example, White fathers were viewed primarily as moral teachers during the colonial phase of American history. Only by considering the fathers' performance of these various roles and by taking into account their relative importance in the socioecological contexts concerned can researchers evaluate fathers' impact on child development.

The Protector

Male leads who are fathers in romance will sometimes demonstrate a protective streak. They have a strong sense of responsibility and commitment to ensuring the emotional and physical well-being of their children and might even put themselves in danger to shield them from harm. This portrayal of protectiveness can really resonate with readers, because it taps into our desire to feel safe and loved, both in romantic relationships and within the family unit.

No surprise, since he's descended from a warrior tribe. I don't want to give spoilers, but there's a point in the story where he's not only determined that no harm will come to his son, he risks bodily harm to ensure it.

Unfortunately, theorists and social commentators have tended in the past to emphasize only one paternal role at a time, with different functions attracting most attention during different historical epochs. Although fathers have typically been perceived and judged by their breadwinning or provisioning, fathers fill other roles as well.

Influence emotional and psychological development: Strong and trusting connections with the father help the child feel calm and safe. The child feels accepted and loved, which boosts their self confidence. **Ensure psychological stability:** A father who responds to the emotional needs of the child, provides support, and offers advice helps the child manage stress and solve problems.

Compared with mothers, fathers indeed spend a greater proportion of their time with children engaged in play, but they still spend a small proportion of their own time in play. This enhanced salience may increase fathers' influence more than would be expected based on the amount of time they spend with their children. However, comparative studies, in which fathers' interactions are contrasted with those of mothers, typically focus on mean-level differences in parenting activities and often obscure common patterns of parent-child interaction. By highlighting the unique qualities of fathers and mothers, they may promote narrow views of fathers' and mothers' roles, thereby failing to capture similarities in the meaning or degree of influence parents exert on their children.

A second line of research on fatherhood examines fathers' effects on children and the pathways through which those effects are exerted. Which aspects of child development were influenced most, at what ages, under which circumstances, and why? Three types of studies have been designed to explore this topic: correlational studies, studies of father absence and divorce, and studies of involved fathers. Here, we review these research methods and then examine direct and indirect effects of fathering on child development.

Social Support Paternal behavior is undoubtedly affected by members of a father's social networks, particularly his relationships with the mother of his child. The roles that fathers play in family life and whether or not they reside with mothers or their children often depend on mothers' attitudes and expectations (Allen & Hawkins, 1999).

Mothers are gatekeepers when it comes to nonresidential fathers' access to children, and they frequently constrain and define the roles and responsibilities of both residential and nonresidential fathers. Mothers communicate their expectations of their partners by handing over their babies for diapering, instead of diapering the baby themselves, for example. Likewise, subtle maternal grimaces when fathers fail to console their crying infants may lead them to "leave the nurturing to mom." In other cases, mothers may use children as bait to get what they want (money, sexual interest) from their partners.

Many women apparently prefer to maintain authority in the child-care arena even if that means physical and mental exhaustion. Their resistance is likely to persist until fundamental changes within society at large change the basic distribution of power. Economic conditions seem unlikely to reduce the need for both parents to obtain employment, and women continue to emphasize the need for husbands and fathers to be family breadwinners (O'Hare, 1995). Within individual families, agreement between mothers and fathers regarding paternal roles may be of crucial importance. As mentioned earlier, family dynamics are formatively significant because fundamental conflicts between the parents have adverse effects on children's development.

Over the last three decades, fathers have embraced much broader and more diverse definitions of their roles and have been increasingly willing to engage in a broad array of activities typically viewed as components of mothering. These changes have taken place alongside smaller changes in the extent to which fathers devote time to activities with and for their children, as well as surprising resistance to the assumption of parental responsibility.

Conclusion

Both the observed changes and their slow pace appear attributable to secular changes, particularly in economic circumstances and maternal employment, as well as to feminist critiques of traditional social structures. In addition, these slow but significant changes in the behavior of men who live with their children

Attempts to understand paternal influences on child development must thus consider the roles, functions, and impacts of father-child relationships, the effects on child development of fatherless lifestyles, and the processes that lead to these circumstances. The multiple roles that fathers are expected to play and the roles that they are actually able to fulfill illustrate the need for researchers to explore multiple dimensions of fathering, fathers' views about aspects of fathering, family decision making and motivation, and the mechanisms through which parents exert influence on children. By elucidating associations among different aspects of fathering and recognizing how and when fathers' attention to certain areas of involvement limits their potential involvement in other ways, researchers will come closer to understanding the unique confluence of factors that affect the course of children's development, as well as the multitude of configurations that characterize positively involved fathers.

Just like being a mother, being a father is no easy task. Based on the number of single dad romance novels published each year, we definitely like seeing our heroes in the role of nurturer and protector, and fall hard for the ones who are overwhelmed but have good intentions. They add depth to the stories and enhance the characterization of the heroes.

As indicated earlier, most researchers have focused on early development, particularly infancy. Studies have revealed that men develop strong attachments to their infants, but that these relationships and their effects on childhood functioning have to be understood in the context of children's other relationships and cultural experiences. Research on fathers over the past 40 years has shifted toward multilevel analyses. The diverse ways in which children's experiences and memories influence later personality is in part rejection of the complexity of family and other interactions to which children are exposed. To all the fathers and father figures, I hope you feel appreciated and celebrated on your day. Just like being a mother, being a father is no easy task. Based on the number of single dad romance novels published each year, we definitely like seeing our heroes in the role of nurturer and protector, and fall hard for the ones who are overwhelmed but have good intentions. They add depth to the stories and enhance the characterization of the heroes.

To all the fathers and father figures, I hope you feel appreciated and celebrated on your day.

REFERENCES:

1. Adams, P. L., Milner, J. R., & Schrepf, N. A. (1984). *Fatherless children*. New York: Wiley.

2. Allen, S. M., & Hawkins, A. J. (1999). Maternal gatekeeping: Mothers' beliefs and behavior that inhibit greater father involvement in family work. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 61, 199–212.
3. Bellinger, D. C., & Gleason, J. B. (1982). Sex differences in parental directives to young children. *Sex Roles*, 8, 1123–1139.
4. Belsky, J., Gilstrap, B., & Ravine, M. (1984). The Pennsylvania Infant and Family Development Project: 1. Stability and change in mother-infant and father-infant interaction at one, three, and nine months. *Child Development*, 55, 692–705.
5. Berman, P. W. (1980). Are women more responsive than men to the young? A review of developmental situational variables. *Psychological Bulletin*, 88, 668–695.
6. Biller, H. B. (1971). *Father, child, and sex role*. Lexington, MA: Heath
7. Cummings, E. M., & O'Reilly, A. W. (1997). Fathers in family context: Effects of marital quality on child adjustment. In M. E. Lamb (Ed.), *The role of the father in child development* (3rd ed., pp. 69–65, 315–325). New York: Wiley.
8. Dalton-Hummel, D. (1982). Syntactic and conversational characteristics of fathers' speech. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 11, 465–483. Day, R. D., & Lamb, M. E. (Eds.). (in press). *Conceptualizing and measuring father involvement*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
9. Easterbrooks, M. A., & Goldberg, W. A. (1984). Toddler development in the family: Impact of father involvement and parenting characteristics. *Child Development*, 55, 740–752